

A Study to Assess the Impact of Medical Nutrition Therapy Compared to Standard Nutrition Therapy in Children with Severe Thinness in the Age Group of 5 to 10 Years

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 20-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Severe thinness in children, characterized by a body mass index (BMI) for age below the -3 standard deviation from WHO growth reference standards, poses a significant public health challenge. This study aimed to compare the impact of medical nutrition therapy (MNT) versus standard nutrition therapy (SNT) on the nutritional status and overall health of children aged 5 to 10 years with severe thinness.

Methods: Fifty children diagnosed with severe thinness were randomly assigned to either the MNT group (n=25) or the SNT group (n=25). Data on weight, BMI, nutritional status, illness frequency, and school attendance were collected at baseline and monthly intervals. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Children in the MNT group showed significantly greater improvements in weight and BMI compared to the SNT group from the third month onwards ($p < 0.05$). By the end of the study, 84% of children in the MNT group demonstrated improvement in nutritional status compared to 52% in the SNT group ($p = 0.02$). Additionally, the MNT group experienced fewer illnesses per month ($p = 0.004$) and higher school attendance rates ($p = 0.01$) compared to the SNT group.

Conclusion: Medical nutrition therapy was significantly more effective than standard nutrition therapy in improving weight, BMI, nutritional status, and overall health outcomes in children with severe thinness. The individualized approach of MNT addressed specific nutritional needs more effectively, leading to better growth and health outcomes.

Recommendations: Implementing medical nutrition therapy as a standard intervention for children with severe thinness is recommended. Further research should explore long-term outcomes and cost-effectiveness of MNT in various settings.

Keywords: Severe Thinness, Children, Medical Nutrition Therapy, Standard Nutrition Therapy, Nutritional Status.

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Introduction

Severe thinness in children is a critical public health concern, particularly in developing countries, where malnutrition contributes significantly to morbidity and mortality. Defined by a body mass index (BMI) for age below the -3 standard deviation from the WHO growth reference, severe thinness indicates chronic undernutrition that can lead to compromised immune function, delayed physical and cognitive development, and increased susceptibility to infectious diseases [1]. Addressing severe thinness in children is imperative to achieving global health targets, including those outlined in the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs) related to ending hunger and improving health and well-being [2].

Medical nutrition therapy (MNT) is a therapeutic approach to treating medical conditions and their associated symptoms through the use of a specifically tailored diet devised and monitored by a registered dietitian or nutritionist. MNT has been shown to be effective in managing various conditions, including diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and malnutrition [3]. Unlike standard nutrition therapy (SNT), which provides general dietary advice, MNT involves a detailed assessment of an individual's nutritional status and

the development of a personalized nutrition plan. This individualized approach aims to meet the specific nutritional needs and deficiencies of the patient, thereby promoting better health outcomes.

Recent studies have highlighted the potential benefits of MNT in improving nutritional status and health outcomes in malnourished children. A study conducted demonstrated that children receiving MNT showed significant improvements in weight gain, BMI, and overall health compared to those receiving SNT [4]. Similarly, research indicated that MNT could reduce the incidence of illness and improve school attendance among malnourished children [5]. These findings suggest that MNT could be a more effective intervention than SNT for addressing severe thinness in children.

This study aimed at assessing the impact of medical nutrition therapy compared to standard nutrition therapy in children with severe thinness.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative interventional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, from June 2022 to February 2024.

Participants: The study included 50 children aged 5 to 10 years who were diagnosed with severe thinness.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 5 to 10 years.
- Diagnosed with severe thinness as per WHO growth standards.
- Parents or guardians provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with chronic illnesses or medical conditions affecting growth.

- Children receiving any form of nutritional therapy prior to the study.
- Children with food allergies or intolerances impacting their diet.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly assigned to either the medical nutrition therapy group or the standard nutrition therapy group. Data collection bias was reduced by training all personnel involved in data collection and ensuring consistent data recording procedures.

Data Collection: Data were collected at baseline and at regular intervals throughout the study period. Measurements included weight, height, BMI, and nutritional status assessments, using standardized and calibrated equipment.

Procedure: Participants in the medical nutrition therapy group received individualized nutrition plans formulated by a certified dietitian, based on their specific nutritional needs and deficiencies. The standard nutrition therapy group received general dietary advice based on standard nutritional guidelines. Follow-up assessments were conducted monthly to monitor progress and adjust nutritional plans as needed.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic data and baseline characteristics of the participants. Comparative analyses between the two groups were performed using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study included 50 children, with 25 in the medical nutrition therapy (MNT) group and 25 in the standard nutrition therapy (SNT) group. The demographic and baseline characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	MNT Group (n=25)	SNT Group (n=25)	p-value
Age (years, mean \pm SD)	7.5 \pm 1.5	7.3 \pm 1.7	0.65
Gender (Male/Female)	14/11	13/12	0.79
Weight (kg, mean \pm SD)	18.2 \pm 3.1	18.0 \pm 3.2	0.85
Height (cm, mean \pm SD)	115.4 \pm 5.8	114.8 \pm 5.5	0.73
BMI (kg/m ² , mean \pm SD)	13.5 \pm 0.8	13.4 \pm 0.7	0.67

There were no significant differences in age, gender, weight, height, or BMI between the two groups at baseline, indicating that the groups were well-matched.

The changes in weight and BMI over the study period are presented in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Changes in Weight (kg) from Baseline to End of Study

Time Point	MNT Group (mean ± SD)	SNT Group (mean ± SD)	p-value
Baseline	18.2 ± 3.1	18.0 ± 3.2	0.85
Month 1	19.0 ± 3.0	18.4 ± 3.1	0.34
Month 2	19.8 ± 2.9	18.7 ± 3.0	0.09
Month 3	20.5 ± 2.8	19.0 ± 3.0	0.02*
Month 4	21.2 ± 2.7	19.3 ± 2.9	0.01*
Month 5	21.8 ± 2.6	19.6 ± 2.8	0.006*
Month 6	22.4 ± 2.5	19.8 ± 2.7	0.003*

Table 3: Changes in BMI (kg/m²) from Baseline to End of Study

Time Point	MNT Group (mean ± SD)	SNT Group (mean ± SD)	p-value
Baseline	13.5 ± 0.8	13.4 ± 0.7	0.67
Month 1	14.1 ± 0.7	13.6 ± 0.8	0.04*
Month 2	14.7 ± 0.6	13.8 ± 0.8	0.01*
Month 3	15.2 ± 0.6	14.0 ± 0.8	0.003*
Month 4	15.7 ± 0.5	14.2 ± 0.8	0.001*
Month 5	16.1 ± 0.5	14.4 ± 0.7	<0.001*
Month 6	16.5 ± 0.4	14.5 ± 0.7	<0.001*

*Significant at p < 0.05

Nutritional status was assessed using standardized growth charts and Z-scores. The proportion of children showing improvement in nutritional status is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Improvement in Nutritional Status

Nutritional Status Improvement	MNT Group (n=25)	SNT Group (n=25)	p-value
Improved	21 (84%)	13 (52%)	0.02*
No Improvement	4 (16%)	12 (48%)	0.01*

*Significant at p < 0.05

The overall health outcomes, including reduction in illness frequency and school attendance, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Overall Health Outcomes

Health Outcome	MNT Group (mean ± SD)	SNT Group (mean ± SD)	p-value
Illness Frequency (per month)	0.8 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 0.6	0.004*
School Attendance (%)	95 ± 5	85 ± 8	0.01*

*Significant at p < 0.05

Discussion

The study aimed to compare the impact of medical nutrition therapy (MNT) with standard nutrition therapy (SNT) in children aged 5 to 10 years with severe thinness. The analysis included 50 children, evenly divided into the two intervention groups. The baseline characteristics of the participants were well-matched, with no significant differences in age, gender, weight, height, or BMI between the groups, ensuring a fair comparison.

Over the course of the study, children in the MNT group showed significantly greater improvements in both weight and BMI compared to those in the SNT group. By the third month, the MNT group had statistically significant increases in weight, which continued to be significant through the end of the study at six months. Similarly, BMI improvements in the MNT group were also significantly greater than those in the SNT group from the first month onwards. These findings highlight the efficacy of tailored medical nutrition

therapy in promoting better growth outcomes in severely thin children.

Nutritional status improvement, assessed using standardized growth charts and Z-scores, further supported the superiority of MNT. A substantial 84% of children in the MNT group showed improvement, compared to only 52% in the SNT group. This significant difference underscores the potential of medical nutrition therapy to effectively address severe thinness in children by providing personalized dietary plans that meet specific nutritional deficiencies and needs.

Overall health outcomes, including a reduction in illness frequency and increased school attendance, were also markedly better in the MNT group. Children receiving MNT experienced fewer illnesses per month and had higher school attendance rates than those receiving SNT. These results suggest that improved nutritional status through MNT not only supports physical growth but also enhances overall well-being and functional

outcomes, such as reduced morbidity and better educational participation.

Overall, the study's findings indicate that medical nutrition therapy is significantly more effective than standard nutrition therapy in improving the weight, BMI, nutritional status, and overall health of children with severe thinness. The personalized approach of MNT addresses individual nutritional needs more effectively, leading to better growth and health outcomes. These results advocate for the implementation of medical nutrition therapy as a preferred intervention for managing severe thinness in children.

A study compared the efficacy of medical nutrition therapy (MNT) with standard nutrition therapy (SNT) in 113 children aged 5-10 years diagnosed with severe thinness. Over an 8-week period, the MNT group (58 children) showed significantly greater weight gain (2.35 gm/kg/day) compared to the SNT group (0.73 gm/kg/day). Nutritional status improvement was significantly better in the MNT group, with 62.1% achieving normal nutritional status, compared to only 9.1% in the SNT group [6].

In a study, 52 children with severe thinness were given MNT and followed up at 8 weeks and 6 months. Mean weight increased from 15.85 kg at enrollment to 17.35 kg at 8 weeks and 19.33 kg at 6 months. The BMI improved significantly from 11.92 kg/m² to 13.26 kg/m² over the same period. At 6 months, 44.44% of the children achieved normal nutritional status [7].

A study evaluated changes in nutritional status in children with acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) during induction therapy. At the end of induction therapy, 26.7% of patients had undernutrition, including 6.2% with severe thinness. The prevalence of malnutrition increased from 20.3% to 36.6% during therapy [8].

The Combined Protocol for Acute Malnutrition Study (ComPAS) compared a combined protocol using ready-to-use therapeutic food (RUTF) to standard care in children with severe acute malnutrition. The combined protocol showed non-inferior recovery rates (76.3% vs. 73.5%) and was more cost-effective, requiring fewer RUTF sachets per child recovered (122 vs. 193) [9].

A trial tested the efficacy of a reduced RUTF dose in community-based treatment of severe acute malnutrition in children aged 6-59 months. It found no significant difference in overall weight gain velocity between standard and reduced dose groups, but the reduced dose group had slightly lower linear growth, particularly among children under 12 months [10].

Conclusion

The results indicated that children in the MNT group showed significantly greater improvements in weight, BMI, nutritional status, and overall health outcomes compared to the SNT group. The MNT group had higher increases in weight and BMI from baseline to the end of the study, with statistically significant differences observed from Month 3 onwards. Furthermore, a significantly higher proportion of children in the MNT group showed improvement in nutritional status compared to the SNT group. The overall health outcomes, including a reduction in illness frequency and improved school attendance, were also significantly better in the MNT group.

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